

Effects of Vee-Diagram Strategy on Achievement and Retention in Gravitation Concept Among Federal College of Education Students, Kano State.

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Abstract

Vee-diagram is one of the learners' centered strategies which makes learning meaningful and worthwhile. The main objective of this study was to investigate effects of vee-diagram strategy on achievement and retention in gravitation concept among Federal College of Education students, Kano State. Pretest and posttest quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study. An intact class of 85 N.C.E. II Physics pre-service teachers during the 2019/2020 academic session were purposively selected for the study. Two research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. Physics Achievement Test (PAT) was used for data collection. The reliability coefficient for the instruments was found to be 0.933 via test retest. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while Z-test was used to test both hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results revealed that there was no significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female students when taught the concept of gravitation using the Vee-Diagram instructional strategy. Also, there was no significant difference in the retention levels of male and female students when taught the concept of gravitation using the Vee-Diagram Instructional Strategy. Based on the findings, it was concluded that the Vee-diagram is a gender friendly instructional strategy, it was therefore recommended that science teachers should employ the use of Vee-diagram as an instructional strategy.

Keywords: Vee-Diagram Instructional Strategy, Academic Achievement, Retention, Gender Stereotypes, and Physics.

Introduction

We observe a lot of cause-effect phenomena in and around our world which are sometimes periodic. Sometimes, based on our instincts, we find solution to a problem or navigate around natural occurrences. There are times we make guesses or speculations about physical quantities and at other times, after a number of trial and errors, we make exact measurements. Physics is the subject, a branch of science that helps us to make a meaning out of our observations by helping to not only connect the dots but offer explanations about these cause-effect relationships and provide tested equations and formulas that takes off the burden of guessing which is why every definition of physics highlights the interaction between space, energy, matter and time. According to Ede and Anosike (2023), physics is one of the core areas of study that supports the physical universe and is always relevant to people's day-to-day lives. Okeke and Ukoh (2020) believes that Physics is crucial for understanding contemporary technology and driving innovation, as it is applied to create tools and equipment used in various fields like military, transportation, medical, and telecommunication. Ahmad and Osiboye (2021) notes that Physics is a subject that should be at the top of the priority list for those involved in science education, for a variety of reasons, including its capacity to aid in our understanding of the world and the significant role it plays in science and technology toward the advancement of any country. Unfortunately, important as physics is, like every other endeavor with immense capabilities to make impact, the teaching and learning of physics is not devoid of besetting challenges with the most prominent being low academic achievement.

Ezugwu and Oguguo (2022) defines academic achievement as a student's current scholastic position. It speaks to the manner in which a person might exhibit their intellectual prowess. This academic standing may be explained by the grades earned in a particular course or set of courses. The scholastic standing of students in physics as a subject or course of study leaves more to be desired and this could account for why Oluwadamilare and Ayanwale (2021) asserts that until Nigeria maybe becomes sufficiently independent in the field of science, technology, and innovation (STI), the debates around the low academic achievement of its physics students will continue to gain traction among scientific educators. This is mainly because there is no longer in question how important physics and physics education are to the country's autonomy in STI.

Generally speaking, the term gender is used to classify human beings into male and female for the purpose of differentiation. Astalini, et al (2021) aptly described gender differences as distinctions between male and female features, traits, and modes of thought, with women's thought processes being more pronounced and their emotions better structured than those of men, who tend to be more practical or to use their wits more. On the other hand, gender stereotypes according to Sriwijayanti et al (2023) are commonly held ideas that impact how people see and behave in society regarding the qualities, positions, and obligations that are considered suitable for men and women. Similarly, Peter and Pathak (2023) opined that Gender stereotypes are based on how people act, behave, or handle their personalities. People of all genders are expected to act and behave in accordance with their defined gender, and when they don't, it serves as a platform for gender inequality, also known as gender discrimination. Gender stereotypes are inflexible beliefs about the traits and conduct that men and women should exhibit. They are frequently founded on out-of-date data and can result in discrimination and opportunity limitations. Again, Döring (2021). Highlights Gender stereotypes as ideas about roles, actions, personalities, and physical characteristics that define what men and women are or ought to be; these ideas frequently mirror orthodox ideas of what it means to be a man or a woman. These perceived differences and stereotypes seem to dictate to each gender consciously or otherwise the kind of endeavors they should venture into regardless of their potentials and capabilities, and these stereotypical ideologies reflect in physics as a subject area.

According to Krakehl and Kelly (2021). When taking student gender and ethnicity into account, there has been a continuous disparity in access to, and performance in advanced high school physics. In the same vein, Ogonna and Iliya (2023) observed that women are underrepresented in many science-related fields in Nigerian secondary schools and colleges, especially in physics-related professions. Research studies also show that women generally perform worse in physics-related professions. For these reasons, the impact of gender differences in physics achievement has been a source of concern for education stakeholders over time. As a testament to this unpleasant development being a universal status-quo, Kalender et al (2022) notes that the American higher education physics community has spent the last few decades addressing issues pertaining to the under representation of women in the field. Additionally, since success in physics is often attributed to brilliance, many students are likely to have fixed mindsets about the subject, which can be particularly harmful for students from underrepresented groups. Stoeckel and Roehrig (2021) points out that women are underrepresented in the field of physics, which is firmly dominated by men. Research indicates that women tend to report a lower sense of competence in the form of self-efficacy than their male peers and that they have a weaker physics identity than men. This underrepresentation is seen not only among professional physicists but also at all levels of physics education. There is a tendency for the younger generation of females to continue to perceive physics as a strictly male endeavor and as a difficult subject area unless they begin to witness a change in the narrative which will begin by high flying female achievers in the subject, and consequently a boost in

representation. This is where a transition from the conventional chalk and board method of teaching physics, to student centered instructional strategies such as the vee-diagram becomes essential.

According to Kayacan (2018), in courses such as physics which contain a lot of abstract concepts, it is extremely important for students to learn by discovery in order to achieve meaningful learning. The Vee diagram, is one of the most appropriate and important documents that could be used in the process of learning through experience because it is effective as a technique that contributes to meaningful learning. Hapsari et al (2012) defines the Vee-diagram instructional strategy as a visual tool that helps students organize and connect concepts, facilitating guided inquiry and enhancing critical thinking in learning processes. Hindriana (2016) views the Vee diagram as an instructional strategy which visually connects conceptual and methodological aspects of learning, facilitating meaningful understanding and reducing cognitive load. Remarkably, authors' views and beliefs about the vee-diagram is that it enhances meaningful learning because the students are actively involved in their learning process which means it can be expected to bring about a desired outcome in students' academic achievement and by extension their retention levels.

According to Lindsey et al. (2014) the human memory is not perfect. Therefore, means have to be constantly sought to facilitate the conservation of knowledge and skills acquired for a long-term duration. Yet students at every level of education have to constantly put up with the challenge of reviewing loads of previously encountered materials and get acquainted with newer ones. Ferreira et al (2016) pointed out that teachers ensure that their students acquire new knowledge and skills but they also must not lose sight of the fact that newly acquired knowledge by itself does not stay put and because of this, has a great tendency to be forgotten. This is why Ahmad (2017) believes that students will only retain information that they find worthwhile and it therefore follows that when the learner is actively involved in the learning process, wherein new knowledge is integrated with relevant existing knowledge, concepts are better organized and retention is improved. Edwards et al (2017) stressed that the importance of retention of knowledge cannot be overemphasized as it is highly necessary for the future application of concepts. If students are to score good grades, progress academically and career wise, and if schools will continue to exist, then the concept of knowledge retention must take top priority this is especially so because the stakes for testing students' knowledge is constantly rising higher. To this end researchers have made efforts to pin point vital learning components that facilitates long-term learning. Their finding is that visual information and problem-solving practice must go hand in hand to foster knowledge retention. From the foregoing discourse, the major thing that boosts retention of knowledge is for the students to be actively involved and participate fully in the learning process. It will be difficult for them to lose sight of their own contributions, and recalling their own efforts is the path that leads them to what the lesson was all about. This is the same thing that plays out when students engage in group discussions. Vee-diagram provides an opportunity for the students to be actively involved in the buildup of the lesson, which will aid in retention.

Physics as a subject area regardless of how it is being perceived, ideally should be offered by both male and female students with both genders performing well in it because potentials are innate and can be nurtured to life when given the opportunity. Unfortunately, societal stereotypes have conditioned the females to believing that physics is a predominantly male subject and worse still, the few females who offer the subject are more often than not out-performed by their male counterparts. According to Chukwuemeka and Bature (2023), women in Nigeria's secondary school and colleges of education are underrepresented and tend to perform poorly in science-related fields, particularly in physics, due to factors such as prior learning, job objectives, self-efficacy, mentality and epistemology. Krzaklewska, Sekuła, Ciaputa, and Struzik (2019) reports that, combined data across all scientific disciplines reveals that women's representation in the natural sciences is much lower in most European countries than in other fields. This is evident from the fact that, in 2015, the proportion of female researchers in higher education ranged from 21% to 54% in the natural sciences and 37% to 70% in the medical and health sciences. Additionally, women make up only 25% of all researchers in the fields of physics and astronomy. Researchers, having identified this trend have over the years attempted to unravel the reasons behind it and thereby proffer solutions and even though other science subjects are beginning to experience a little bit of a boost in women representation, the same cannot be said for physics. The possible long run impact of this development is that the current generation of women will continue to doubt and underrate their capabilities and at the same time reinforce the belief that physics is a male only subject. Before long, the younger generation completely losses interest in the subject and the situation goes from underrepresentation to zero representation which will not only affect Physics as a discipline but other science related profession because of the essentiality of physics as a subject to these professions. To curb the situation from getting any worse than it already is, it becomes expedient to seek for interventions. Although stakeholders have employed various means to address the situation ranging from mentorship to sensitization and scholarships, this study seeks to investigate the effect of vee-diagram which is a student-centered strategy on the academic achievement and retention levels of the female students in comparison with that of their male counterparts.

Objectives of the study

The objective of this research study is to determine effects of vee-diagram strategy on achievement and retention in gravitation concept among Federal College of Education students, Kano State. Specifically, the study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. To determine the effect of Vee-Diagram on academic achievement in concept gravitation based on gender among FCE, Kano Students
2. To determine the effect of Vee-Diagram on retention in concept of gravitation based on gender among FCE, Kano Students.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught the concept gravitation in FCE, Kano?
2. What is the mean retention scores of male and female students taught the concept gravitation in FCE, Kano?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at $P=0.05$ level of significance.

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught the concept gravitation in FCE, Kano.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students taught the concept gravitation in FCE, Kano.

Methodology

The research design adopted for the study is pretest-posttest quasi experimental research design. The quasi-experimental design by nature is a design that sets out to test or verify the effect of a particular intervention or treatment on a group of subjects. In this study, the quasi-experimental design was adopted to determine the effect of Vee-diagram on students' academic achievement and retention based on gender. One group of students were used for data collection. The intact class of males and females were pretested to determine their ability and confirm their equivalence. Thereafter, the class was taught the concept of gravitation using Vee-diagram. At the end of the six weeks treatment period, a posttest was administered to the class to determine the effectiveness of the Vee-diagram. After two weeks, a post-posttest was administered to the class to determine the retention abilities of the students. The same questions were asked for the pre-test, post-test and post-posttest. However, the questions were rearranged for the post-posttest to forestall familiarity of the students with the questions. The population for this study is the entire N.C.E. two students of Federal College of Education Kano in the 2019/2020 session. The intact class of 85 (64 males and 21 females) physics students was purposively selected to serve as the sample for the study.

A researcher designed Physics Achievement Test (PAT) was used to measure students' achievement and retention in the concept of gravitation. The PAT which was developed based on the concept of gravitation, contained thirty (30) multiple choice test items with four (4) options lettered A, B, C, D for the students to pick the correct option in each item. The test was administered as a pre-test to determine the equivalence of both genders, as a post-test to determine the effect of the intervention on academic achievement and as a post-post test to determine the retention level of both genders. In order to ensure the validity of the instruments, PAT items and the lesson plans were given to one professor in the Department of Physics, Bayero University Kano and one Senior lecturer (PhD) in the Department of Physics Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi. The scores obtained from the pilot testing were analyzed using the Pearson-Product Moment Correlation Coefficient at the 0.05 significance level to determine the reliability coefficient of the PAT which was found to be 0.93.

The class was taught using the Vee-diagram for two hours per week for six (6) weeks using Lesson plans developed by the researchers. The teaching took place within the normal periods scheduled by the department for PHY 213 so that an already planned school routine is not disrupted. The Vee-diagram is both a teaching and learning strategy but was solely used as a teaching strategy in this study. As the name implies, the teaching outline follows a V template. The lesson starts out from the left wing of the Vee-diagram which is the conceptual wing, heads towards the event and goes back up to the right wing which is the methodological wing. The conceptual wing was outlined, and focus questions set by the researchers, while the events and methodological (doing) wing were purely carried out by the students. The focus question is placed between both wings. The topic for each period was presented alongside the instructional materials and the lesson followed the order of the flowchart below:

Figure 1: Flow Chart for the use of Vee-diagram (Researcher Designed)

The scores that were obtained from the pre-test, post-test and the post-posttest were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) to answer the two research questions raised. To test the hypotheses, the data were subjected to Z-test at 0.05 level of significance. The scores obtained were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: What is the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught the concept gravitation in FCE, Kano?

To answer the research Question, the posttest scores of the male and female students were subjected to descriptive statistics using mean and standard deviation as shown in table 1 below.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Posttest Scores of Male and Female Students

	GENDER	N	Mean	S. D.	Mean Diff.
POSTTEST	Male	64	14.4844	4.90219	1.2299
	Female	21	15.7143	3.27327	

The results in Table 1 above shows that the male students had a mean and standard deviation of 14.48 and 4.90 respectively while the female students had a mean of 15.71 and standard deviation of 3.27 with a mean difference of 1.22 in favor of the female students that had higher mean. This shows that there is difference in the academic achievement of male and female students taught using the Vee-diagram instruction.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught the concept gravitation in FCE, Kano. To test null hypothesis 1, the post-test scores of the male and female students were subjected to independent sample Z-test statistic The summary of the analysis is presented in table 2 below.

Table 2: Independent sample Z-test for academic achievement of Male and Female students

	Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	S E, Mean	df	Z	p	Decision
POSTTEST	Male	64	14.48	4.90	0.61	83	1.072	0.287	Accepted
	Female	21	15.71	3.27	0.71				

Results from Table 2 shows that the Z-cal is 1.072 and the observed p-value is 0.287 which is greater than the significant 0.05 α value with $df=83$, hence, the null hypothesis is thereby accepted implying that there is no significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female students in the experimental group.

Research Question Two: What is the mean retention scores of male and female students taught the concept gravitation in FCE, Kano?

Descriptive statistic in form of mean and standard deviation was used to answerer research question two and is presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Mean and S.D of Post-Posttest Scores of Male and Female Physics Students Exposed to Vee-Diagram Instructional Strategy

Group	N	Post Mean	-Test Std. Deviation	Post - Mean	Posttest Std. Deviation	Mean Gain
Male	64	14.48	4.90	14.82	4.96	0.34
Female	21	15.71	3.27	15.38	3.30	0.33

Table 3 indicates the mean post-posttest scores of male and female physics students exposed to Vee-Diagram Instructional Strategy. The result revealed that female students had post-test mean achievement score of 15.71 and standard deviation of 3.27, post-posttest mean achievement score of 15.38 and standard deviation of 3.30 with mean gain of 0.33 while male students had a mean post-test achievement score of 14.48 and standard deviation of 4.90, post-posttest mean achievement score of 14.82 and standard deviation of 4.96 with mean gain of 0.34. The mean gain difference between male and female achievement score is 0.01. This indicates that female physics students performed slightly higher than their male counterpart.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students taught the concept gravitation in FCE, Kano. Hypothesis two was tested by subjecting the post-posttest mean achievement (retention) score of male and female students to independent sample z-test and the summary is presented in table 4 below.

Table 4: Independent Sample Z-Test for Post-Posttest Mean Achievement (Retention) Scores of the Male and Female Physics Students Exposed to Vee-Diagram Instructional Strategy

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	Z-value	P-value	Decision
Male	64	14.82	4.96	83	-.476	.635	Accepted
Female	21	15.38	3.30				

Table 4 presents an Independent Sample Z-Test for Post-Posttest Mean Achievement (Retention) scores of the Male and Female Physics Students Exposed to Vee-Diagram Instructional Strategy. From the result, the observed p-value is .635 with $df=83$ and the alpha value is 0.05. The observed p-value 0.635 is greater than the alpha value 0.05. The null hypothesis is hereby retained or accepted. The reason for acceptance of the null hypothesis is that the observe p-value is greater than the alpha value. Therefore, there was no significant difference in the mean retention score between male and female students taught physics using Vee-Diagram Instructional Strategy. Hence Vee-Diagram Instructional Strategy is gender friendly teaching strategy.

Summary of findings

1. The findings from research hypothesis one showed that although the female students had a higher mean score, there was no significant difference in the performance of both genders and so the null hypothesis “there is no significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female students when taught the concept of gravitation using the Vee-Diagram” is accepted implying that there is no significant difference in gender performance.
2. The findings from research hypothesis two showed that although the female students had a higher mean score, there was no significant difference in the retention levels of both genders and so the null hypothesis “there is no significant difference in the retention levels of male and female students when taught the concept of gravitation using the Vee-Diagram” is accepted implying that there is no significant difference in retention levels based on gender.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined the effect of the vee-diagram strategy on female students’ academic achievement and gravitation concept retention. The two (2) research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation and both hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The students involved in the study were found to be equivalent after a pre-test was conducted and it is believed that the slight difference in mean scores of academic achievement and retention in favor of the females was

as a result of the treatment. The finding from research hypothesis one showed that there is no significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female when taught the concept of gravitation using the Vee-Diagram instructional strategy. The Z-test analysis at p-value of 0.287 which is greater than the alpha value of 0.05 confirmed this. Similarly, the finding from hypothesis two showed that there is no significant difference in the level of retention of male and female students when taught the concept of gravitation of using Vee-Diagram due to the observed p-value of 0.635 which is greater than the alpha value of 0.05. These results show that the Vee-diagram is a gender friendly instructional strategy. Although there is no significant difference in their achievement scores as ascertained by the Z-test, the females had a higher mean score of 15.71 as against their male counterpart which had a mean score of 14.48. Female performance in science subjects has been a major concern for researchers over the years. These findings are a pointer to the fact that these concerns can be well taken care of if student centered instructional strategies like the Vee-Diagram are employed. Judging from the class participation in the course of the study, the results obtained were very much expected as it was observed that the female students were quite enthused and participated fully in each of the six lessons. According to Abdulkadir (2017) whose finding agrees with this present study, the use of epistemological components of Vee-Diagram should be encouraged to enhance the learning of physics concepts by male and female students in physics classrooms and to improve their interaction of conceptual, methodological and problem-solving skills. This is supported by the findings from his study which set out to investigate the “effects of the use of Vee-Diagram on Senior School Students’ performance in Ilorin”. It was found that besides improving significantly the performance of the students, Vee-diagram gave the female students the same opportunity to be at their best just like their male counterparts as there was no significant difference in the performance of both genders. Likewise, supporting these findings is the research of Namasaka et al (2013) as the results obtained from their study indicates that girls and boys taught using CVMS (concept and Vee mapping strategy) had similar post-test scores implying similar motivation levels. It is therefore safe to say that, ranging from cognitive constructs to psychological constructs, vee-diagram positively impacts students’ learning experience thereby bringing about a desired outcome. Again, Harrington et al (2022) conducted a study which focused on two underrepresented groups in UK HE: widening participation and women physics students and it was discovered that there was a substantial correlation between gender and the classification that MPhys (Hons) students received, with a greater percentage of female students graduating with an upper class or first-class classification than male students. Harrington et al implied that it is possible that this group of female students were resilient or were able to lessen the negative impacts of their underrepresentation. It is however necessary to buttress the explanation offered by Harrington et al by stating that when females are exposed to learner centered strategies and equipped with appropriate and sufficient learning tools, they will be at par with their male counterparts. Although this present study set out to investigate the performance of female students, worthy of note is the fact that the vee-diagram also had an effect on the male student’s academic achievement and retention as is evident in their post-test scores. This goes to say that employing the vee-diagram as a tool to combat gender stereotypes is actually a move that generally overhauls the undesirable state of the teaching and learning of physics.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: Vee-Diagram instructional strategy is a gender friendly method of instruction as it was shown that both male and female students performed better in Physics. Vee-Diagram instructional strategy enhanced both male and female students’ retention level as it was indicated that there is no significant difference in retention of gravitation concept between male and female students.

Recommendations

From the findings and conclusions made, the following recommendations are proffered.

1. Curriculum planners and policy makers in education should encourage science teachers to adopt the Vee-Diagram instructional strategy as a teaching strategy because it is a gender friendly strategy which brings to limelight the potentials of female students.
2. Experts in the use of the vee-diagram strategy should seek for and make use of available platforms to train both teachers and students on how to employ the strategy as a teaching and learning tool respectively because of its effectiveness in improving students’ academic achievement.

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